

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF IMPROVING THE CREATIVE AND PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY OF FUTURE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The article contains comments on improving the creative and professional activity of future elementary teachers in the higher education system today, forming the ability to conduct independent research, developing creative thinking, and the problems of engaging in independent scientific activity and their effective solutions.*

Keywords: *education, professional activity, creative activity, future elementary school teachers, research activity, research skills, forecasting method, design method, modeling method, creative thinking, self-awareness, self-determination.*

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ И ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ

Аннотация. *Статья содержит комментарии по совершенствованию творческой и профессиональной деятельности будущих учителей начальных классов в системе высшего образования на сегодняшний день, формированию умения проводить самостоятельные исследования, развитию творческого мышления, проблемам занятия самостоятельной научной деятельностью и их эффективному решению.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, профессиональная деятельность, творческая деятельность, будущие учителя начальных классов, исследовательская деятельность, исследовательские умения, метод прогнозирования, метод проектирования, метод моделирования, творческое мышление, самосознание, самоопределение.*

INTRODUCTION

In the context of socio-economic changes that are taking place in our country, the demand for the quality of customer service is growing at an alarming rate. The social demands placed on the education system are aimed at preparing a proactive student who can take responsibility in the chosen situation, understand the consequences of the decision, is capable of cooperation, and is equipped with integrity and concreteness. On the other hand, the main goal of education is to prepare a qualified student who is competitive in the labor market, who knows his job well and is directed to the relevant field of activity, who has a world-class job in his field of study, continuous professional growth, and social and professional responsibility.

Scientific activity in accordance with the organizational-legal form and administrative mandate of the Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan "On further improvement of the legal framework for the development of scientific-research and innovative activities" dated March 9, 2020, no. 133 The right to participate in the project competition with a set of project documents for the implementation of a research project and to submit the set of documents in accordance with the deadline specified in the announcement has been increased. This involves the formation of a policy for carrying out scientific research work.

The demands placed on the training of the student are increased by the fact that the success and success of his future professional activity and life depends on how the student of the

education prepares for the graduate professional activity, how much he is interested in active creative activity, his needs are formed, self-improvement and professional growth.

The most perfect reproduction of professional activity in the modern environment is the constructive, innovative, creative activity of the entrepreneur. Today, an entrepreneur must be independent, creative, active, proactive, able to make a profit, propose and develop ideas, find unconventional solutions, and implement economically useful projects. This can be done through a person-centered approach to teaching.

The person-oriented approach ends up in the educational system map, which is closed to the holistic development of the personality. The measure of such development is declared as the final result of education, the criterion of the quality of work of a teacher, teacher, administrator, teacher in totality. This approach is aimed at developing the learner's personality, his inner world, abilities, potential, dexterity and justice, goodness and happiness.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The goal of higher education is to awaken the inner strength and potential of a person, to make a full and rapid development of the person. The goal of self-directed education is to support and develop the mechanism of self-control, self-direction, and self-determination in a person, which is the basis for the formation of a personal, unique personality, dialogical interaction with a person, nature, and culture. By this, we understand that the realization of one's potential is the process and result of a person's development of his talents and abilities to the highest level, and the practical application of that. This is also due to the constant self-improvement of the person. Self-awareness is a result of a person's constant striving to align his own actions, actions, aspirations, and interests with the interests, actions, and aspirations of other people, to create social interests in himself, and to lose his personal and personal independence. Determining one's identity is the formation of a person's spiritual and moral identity, recognition of "I" in himself, understanding of his identity in himself, in society, in life. The commitment to the implementation of a person-oriented approach in higher education is reflected in the development of an important direction in the direction of the integration of higher education with improved educational achievement in Japan.

Research is a long, complex, complex process that occurs under the influence of many factors. The successful scientific activity of a student is the biggest factor that is determined not only by his scientific research and professional communication, but also by his scientific research. In future students, it is necessary to form the skills of conducting independent research, that is, to learn how to work with educational and scientific literature, to collect and analyze information, to systematize and summarize facts, and to organize participation in conferences.

An important creative element of the process of improving the creative professional activity of future elementary school teachers is the principles that determine the organization of pedagogical activities to meet the set goals and solve the selected tasks.

The ability to set goals, plan one's work, analyze and evaluate one's own work, think critically, and develop one's own judgment is important for a future elementary school teacher.

That is why the idea of developing a new system of professional training of future students was born. The development of the future teacher's skills is reflected in the state educational curriculum, science curriculum. Hucucan, "Pedagogy, innovation and integration of primary education" science book, it is emphasized that the importance of educational science as a tool in higher vocational education is the formation of improvement of creative and

professional activity of future primary school teachers. Also, in the topic of independent education, which is recommended in this subject book, importance is attached to scientific research, scientific research methodology.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

F. Pakhmatova stated in the research work on improving the creative professional activity of future primary school teachers that the following criteria for the formation of the competence training component for improving the creative professional activity of future primary school teachers are defined as follows:

- positive attitude towards improvement of the creative professional activity of future elementary school teachers (motivational component), acquisition of knowledge about the field of research activity (cognitive component), manifestation of practical research skills (technological component);

- In the analysis of psychological-pedagogical research, the following coefficient of the component of research competence was identified and clarified:

- to improve the creative professional activity of future elementary school teachers, to understand the importance of competent research activity and the need to acquire research competence and apply research skills (motivational component);

- conscious application of knowledge and skills in the field of research activity (cognitive component);

- independent and successful demonstration of the necessary research skills in the performance of educational and professional tasks in the research field (technological component);

- to understand the importance of research competence in the initial activity of the future primary education teacher with the identified components of the research competence, the multiplier of the study and the strong criterion analysis of the study.

N. Narzieva also studied the issue of formation and development of research skills in students. The criterion for determining the formation of research skills in students by the researcher (applicability of the problem, problem solving and selection of solutions, acceptance of the problem, comprehensibility and scientificity of the problem), the integration of the content of the basic competences (aspiration, closure, logical thinking, curiosity, innovation, analytical and synthetic thinking) bepush acocida defined; the method of forecasting, designing, modeling of research activity has been improved in order to determine the optimal pedagogical-psychological principle (logic, systematicity, multifacetedness) of the level of development of research skills; in order to form research skills, it has been improved to use the research-oriented framework of euptic-poductive educational technology (creating a problem situation, forming a learning process, classifying, comparing, systematizing, clarifying, proving); The scientific-methodical support for the development of intellectuality and creativity in students has been improved in the context of general education content, data analysis, quick learning, application, problem and creative exercise complex development. N. Narzieva wrote that improving the creative professional activity of future elementary school teachers is not only the ability of the student to carry out research work, the acquisition of research skills by the student, but also the assimilation of integrative knowledge and skills in the field of science, as well as creative activity in independent development. description will be given.

Also, the solution to improve the creative and professional activity of the future elementary school teachers requires an integrative approach, to solve this, to cover the problem from a comprehensive perspective, and for this, the knowledge obtained from a specific field of study, the element of research in the general education system is dependent only on a specific field of study. manifestation, because the research activity cannot be fully realized in the field of science, and thus the possibility of creative research in the field of teaching science is closed.

In addition, it is necessary to develop the educational and research skills of the students in the research, and to develop the educational and research skills with the modern pedagogical technology directed to the individual (person-oriented, focused on collaborative activities, problem-based research) and the elements of educational activity, and the development and implementation of its methodological system. ibopathy is emphasized.

CONCLUSION

The activity of improving the creative professional activity of the future elementary school teachers in the developed state is broadly understood as an active educational activity that is close to the development of the creative thinking of students and the ability to independently solve problems based on specific problems. Identifying the problem, analyzing the existing research topic, choosing a research topic and topic, research, data collection, interpretation, writing a scientific paper; Japan, the result of which is an intellectual product presented in a compact form.

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